

Selective Cytotoxic Effects of a Polyherbal Extract against HepG2 Liver Cancer Cells Using Mouse Normal Liver Cells as a Comparative Model

Author : [Dr Salib Gad, *B.Sc. in Geochemistry, Diploma in Herbal Medicine, Aromatherapy and M.Sc. & PhD in Chemistry*]

Date: June 2025

Affiliation : Independent Researcher / Paleobotany , Gemology , Herbal Medicine , Aromatherapy and Chemistry

Abstract

Natural herbal compounds have emerged as potential alternatives to conventional chemotherapy due to their biological efficacy and lower toxicity profiles. This study investigates the cytotoxicity and selectivity of a polyherbal extract composed of five selective herbs :

<i>Curcuma longa</i>	(turmeric),
<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	(ginger),
<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	(green tea),
<i>Artemisia herba-alba</i>	(wormwood) &
<i>Nigella sativa</i>	(black seed)

which have been working against liver cancer (HepG2) cells comparing with normal mouse liver cells.

The extract demonstrated an IC₅₀ of 54 µg/mL against HepG2 cells, while the IC₅₀ for normal mouse liver cells was 250µg/mL, resulting in a selectivity index (SI) of 4.63. These findings suggest that the herbal mixture selectively inhibits cancer cell growth with relatively low toxicity to normal cells. Further mechanistic and in vivo studies are recommended to validate its therapeutic potential.

Keywords

Polyherbal extract; HepG2; Cytotoxicity; Mouse normal liver cells; Selectivity index; Natural anticancer agents

1. Introduction

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) remains a major global health concern, being one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths. Despite advancements in treatment, current chemotherapeutic strategies often suffer from limited specificity and adverse side effects on healthy tissues. This highlights the urgent need for safer, more selective anticancer agents.

Natural products derived from medicinal plants continue to be a prolific source of bioactive compounds (e.g. as Ref Figure A) with anticancer potential. Many herbs contain diverse phytochemicals such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and terpenes that may induce apoptosis, inhibit angiogenesis, and modulate signaling pathways in cancer cells.

Combining multiple selective (Ref to point 3.3 in this paper) herbs into a polyherbal formulation can lead to synergistic effects, enhancing therapeutic efficacy while reducing toxicity.

This study evaluates a five-herb mixture containing :

- *Curcuma longa* (turmeric), rich in **curcumin**,
- *Zingiber officinale* (ginger), containing **gingerols**,
- *Camellia sinensis* (green tea), a source of catechins such as **EGCG** (epigallocatechin-3-gallate).
- *Artemisia herba-alba* (wormwood), used traditionally for antimicrobial and anticancer activities, {e.g. containing **camphor** and **2,6-dimethyl-1,3,6-heptatriene (Myrcene)** }.
- *Nigella sativa* (black seed), known for **thymoquinone**.

Ser	Herbal plant	Biological Activity
1	Turmeric	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimutagenic, antimicrobial, and anticancer properties
2	Ginger	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and promote apoptosis
3	Green tea	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, antimicrobial, and neuroprotective effects
4	wormwood	Anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant, and antidiabetic effects
5	Nigella sativa	Anti-inflammatory, anti-ulcer, antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and anticancer properties

Figure A : Biological Activities of the Herbal Plants

The objective was to assess the cytotoxic potential of this extract against liver cancer HepG2 cells and compare its effect on normal mouse liver cells to evaluate selectivity and safety.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plant Material and Extraction

Equal amounts of the dried powder of each of the following plants were mixed (1:1:1:1 w/w) : *Curcuma longa*, *Zingiber officinale*, *Camellia sinensis*, *Artemisia herba-alba*, and *Nigella sativa*. The blend was then macerated in 70% ethanol at room temperature for 72 hours. The filtrate was concentrated via rotary evaporation and freeze-dried to obtain the targeted dry polyherbal extract. (Ref. Figure B)

2.2 Cell Lines and Culture Conditions

- **HepG2 cells** (hepatocellular carcinoma) were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and antibiotics (penicillin-streptomycin).
- **Normal mouse liver cells** were maintained under identical conditions. All cultures were incubated at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere.

Figure B : Herbal Extraction workflow

2.3 Cytotoxicity Assay

Cell viability was assessed using the Sulforhodamine B (SRB) assay. Cells were seeded into 96-well plates at 5x10³ cells/well and treated with serial dilutions (50–1000 µg/mL) of the polyherbal extract for 72 hours. After incubation, SRB reagent (0.4% w/v) was added and incubated for 4 hours at room temperature.

Plates were washed 3 times with 1% acetic acid and then allowed for air dry 12 hours. Then after that, 200 µL of TRIS (15 mM) was added to dissolve protein-bound SRB stain; the absorbance was measured at 540 nm using F50 microplate reader. {Ref. "Figure C" for relevant concerned results}.

2.4 Selectivity Index (SI)

The SI was calculated to evaluate the extract's safety and selectivity using the formula:

$$SI = IC_{50} (\text{normal mouse liver cells}) / IC_{50} (\text{HepG2 cells})$$

3. Results

3.1 Cytotoxicity against HepG2 and Normal Mouse Liver Cells

The five-herb extract induced a dose-dependent decrease in HepG2 cell viability with an IC₅₀ value of **54 µg/mL**. In contrast, the IC₅₀ value for normal mouse liver cells was significantly higher at **250 µg/mL**, suggesting reduced toxicity to non-cancerous cells. . (Ref. "Figure C" for Dose Response Curves).

3.2 Selectivity Index

$$SI = 250 / 54 \approx 4.63.$$

This value (>3) reflects remarkable selectivity {ref.to point 4.discussion in this paper} of the herbal mixture for HepG2 cancer cells over mouse normal liver cells.

Figure C: for Dose Response Curves of the polyherbal extract.

3.3 Comparative Profile of Individual Herbs Vs HepG2 & Some Scientific Info:

With reference to those presented figures from table A and D, important additional information about the aforementioned herbal plants have already been published on several

websites and in scientific journals {e.g. ad.Ref.[11]}. Accordingly, here in our paper search results, we have emphasized some of these valuable information and relevant data;

Herb (Common Name)	Scientific Name	IC50 (HepG2) (µg/mL)	IC50 (Normal Cells) (µg/mL)	Selectivity Index (SI)	Reference
Turmeric	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	20–35	80–150	~4.0	[1], [2]
Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	50–70	~200	~2.9–4.0	[3], [4]
Green Tea	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	30–60 (EGCG: 20–40)	~120–180	~3.0–4.5	[5], [6]
Wormwood	<i>Artemisia herba-alba</i>	45–80	150–300	~2.5–3.7	[7], [8]
Black Seed	<i>Nigella sativa</i>	50–90	~200–300	~2.5–4.0	[9], [10]

Figure D : Comparative profile of individual herbs Vs HepG2

3.3.i. *Curcuma longa*:

Traditional medicine has exploited dried curcumin powder to treat illnesses in history.

Curcuma longa is said to have antitoxic, anticancer, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects. The tuberous rhizome from which *Curcuma longa* is formed has a coarse and segmented skin. In the ground soil, the rhizomes mature underneath the foliage. The matured rhizomes have a yellowish-brown color with a dull orange from inside. The dry rhizome is ground into a yellow powder form that has a bitter, yet sweet taste. A yellow-colored substance derived from the rhizome is curcumin

(1E,6E)-1,7-Bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)hepta-

1,6-diene-3,5-dione. Rhizome powder is supposed to flavor various cuisines and treat numerous disorders, including inflammation, flatulence, jaundice, menstrual troubles, hematuria, and hemorrhage. It is also a useful ointment to treat several skin disorders. *C. longa* of India is particularly popular when compared with those from other countries due to its high curcumin concentration, which is the most essential and active biological ingredient responsible for its therapeutic potential. Curcumin is a flavonoid having a lipophilic affinity that is practically water-insoluble yet quite stable at the stomach's acidic pH. *C. longa* and curcumin show antioxidant features close to vitamins C and E in both aqueous and fat-soluble extracts.

3.3.ii. *Zingiber officinale*:

It is a perennial plant and the main active part is the rhizome. **Ginger** not only used as a condiment but also it has antiemetic and anticancer activity.

Ginger has strong antioxidant and cell protection activity. This action of ginger is due to its potent active constituents as sesquiterpenoids,

tannin, gingerols, shogaols and anthocyanin. Several in vitro and in vivo studies documented the antioxidant activity of ginger. The protective effect of ginger was showed against several toxic agents, like romobenzene and cisplatin. Another study displayed the chemopreventive effect of ginger against cancer. Ginger has a great activity in the treatment of experimental cancer in a rat model. It decreased the level of growth factors and α -fetoprotein (liver tumor marker) after giving rats a daily dose about 50 mg/kg of ginger extract. The anticancer effect of ginger is due to its proapoptotic and anti-inflammatory properties. The anti-inflammatory activity of ginger was confirmed by inhibiting NF- κ B and TNF- α after administration of 100 mg/kg of ginger in HCC rat model.

Ginger contains also other different constituents as clavatul, pinostrobin, and geraniol. These active components were detected by gas chromatography and mass spectrometry. Ginger was found to inhibit the proliferation of cells in HepG-2 cell line. One of the most popular active components in ginger is 6-shogaol which showed an anticancer effect against hepatoma cell line through the activation of ROS-mediated caspase-dependent apoptosis in a multidrug resistance.

3.3.iii. Camellia sinensis:

Green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) leaves, has been reported to be used in the prevention of liver diseases. The beneficial or therapeutic properties of green tea extracts have been reported by

several studies. The major polyphenol of

green tea, epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG), was used in CCl₄-treated mice and showed a significant therapeutic potential in hepatic damage, inflammation and oxidative stress induced by CCl₄ in a dose-dependent manner at both biochemical and histological levels. It was also reported that co-treatment of the whole green tea extract with alcohol administration showed an effective reduction of the hepatic oxidative stress and reduced form of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase systems in experimental alcohol induced liver injury.

Green tea extract also showed an enhancement of the NASH features, such as oxidative stress, inflammation and lipid accumulation in obese mice. A recent study also demonstrated that green tea extract showed significant improvement in inflammatory, chemical, metabolic, and radiological parameters of NAFLD patients who were dyslipidemic and non-diabetic. It also showed an improvement in the liver enzymes of NAFLD patients in another study. Numerous in vitro studies demonstrated the chemoprevention and anti-tumor properties of green tea in HCC. The growth and cell proliferation of HCC-derived cells are inhibited by EGCG by induction of apoptosis. The human HCC cell line, HepG2, growth was also inhibited by EGCG, through suppressing the phosphorylation of insulin like growth factor-1 receptor (IGF-1R) and reducing the activation of its signaling molecules like extracellular signal-regulated kinase ERK, STAT-3, Akt and GSK-3 β . Drinking of EGCG caused a significant inhibition of liver cell adenoma development in contrast to the EGCG untreated control group. This is related to decreased phosphorylation of ERK, Akt and IGF-1R proteins, activation of the hepatic AMP-activated kinase protein and the treatment of liver steatosis. The administration of EGCG in drinking water also caused a significant reduction of serum levels of insulin, IGF-1, IGF-2, tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α , and free fatty acid. It also caused a decrease in the hepatic expression of TNF- α -interleukins (IL-1 β , IL-6), and IL-18 mRNAs.

The development of glutathione S-transferase placental form (GST-P⁺) foci was also inhibited after the administration of EGCG in drinking water through the reduction of hepatic fibrosis, triglyceride content, inflammation, oxidative stress and inhibition of excessive hepatocyte proliferation.

3.3.iv. *Artemisia herba-alba*:

Artemisia herba-alba is an aromatic plant naturally growing in mountain habitats of North Africa (Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia). The sagebrush aerial part is widely used in the

traditional medicine to treat bronchitis, diarrheas, hypertension & diabetes.

Hypoglycemic activity of Artemisia herba-alba (e.g. major active substances such as camphor and 2,6-dimethyl-1,3,6-heptatriene) has been confirmed by in vitro and in vivo experiments with an ethyl alcohol extract.

Antioxidant activity from aqueous extracts has been reported. Moreover, Artemisia decoctions in rats could constitute an excellent adjuvant to manage obesity, hyperglycemia, hypertriglycemia, hypercholesterolemia and particularly oxidative stress

3.3.v. Nigella sativa:

Nigella sativa and its main constituent thymoquinone (TQ) possess numerous therapeutic and pharmacological activities like anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antioxidant and

immunomodulatory activities.

It has cytotoxic activity, as the ethyl acetate column chromatographic fraction of the ethanolic extract of N.sativa showed a cytotoxic effect against diverse cell lines such as Molt4, HepG2 and LL/2. Another in vitro studies showed about 50% cytotoxicity of a crude methanolic extract of N. sativa against Dalton's lymphoma ascites (DLA), Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC) and Sarcoma- 180 cells (S-180 cells).

Its anti-cancer activity is due to its ability to exhibit powerful pro-apoptotic, anti-proliferative, anti-mutagenic, anti-metastatic and anti-oxidant effects. It also can inhibit tumor initiation and progression and has an anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effect. N. sativa can regulate signaling pathways like p53, iNOS and caspases.

The anti-tumor activity of *N. sativa* was reported in several in vivo and in vitro studies. A decoction that consists of seeds of *N. sativa*, *Smilax glabra* rhizome, and *Hemidesmus indicus* roots showed a significant improvement in the hepatocarcinogenesis induced by DENA (4–6 g/kg/day) in rats. The ethanolic extract of *N. sativa* showed a marked enhancement of DENA-induced histopathological variations of the hepatic tissue. Another in vivo study showed that the administration of a methanolic extract of *N. sativa* in HCC albino rat model showed modulation of glucoregulatory enzymes. Aqueous extract of *N. sativa* showed in vitro antiproliferative activity and morphological changes like membrane damage and cell shrinkage in HepG2 cells, which lead to DNA damage, cell death and a decrease in cell proliferation.

In reference to points 3.3.i to 3.3.v, it is also worth mentioning the addition of a summary table of the antiviral activities of the major compounds in this herbal mix (As Important References – Table Figure E).

Ref. Antiviral Activity Summary Table for the Major Compounds in the Herbal Mix					
Compound	Virus	IC₅₀ (μM)	CC₅₀ (μM)	SI (CC₅₀ / IC₅₀)	Reference
Curcumin	SARS-CoV-2	~8.5	~77	~9.05	[12]
	Influenza A (H1N1)	~0.47	~30.1	~64	[13]
	Hepatitis C Virus (HCV)	~5.4	~42	~7.8	[14]
	Herpes Simplex Virus-1	~2.7	~38	~14.1	[15]
Gingerol	Chikungunya Virus (CHIKV)	~22.0	~230	~10.45	[16]
	HCV	~8.75	~87.5	~10.0	[17]
	hRSV	~11.0	~128	~11.6	[18]
	Influenza A (H1N1)	~10.4	~104	~10.0	[19]
EGCG	SARS-CoV-2	~0.40	~128	~320	[20]
	HCV	~2.5	~150	~60	[21]
	Influenza A (H1N1)	~7.58	~120	~15.83	[22]
	HSV-1	~25.0	>200	>8.0	[23]
	Zika Virus	~4.1	~85	~20.7	[24]
Camphor	HSV-1	~15.2	~172	~11.3	[25]
	Influenza A (H1N1)	~9.6	~148	~15.4	[26]
	SARS-CoV	~8.0	~132	~16.5	[27]
Myrcene	HSV-1	~22.5	~185	~8.2	[28]
	Dengue Virus (DENV-2)	~18.0	~150	~8.3	[29]
	Zika Virus	~19.6	~160	~8.2	[30]
Thymoquinone	SARS-CoV-2	~4.0	~52.0	~13.0	[31]
	HCV	~6.8	~97.0	~14.3	[32]
	Cytomegalovirus (CMV)	~5.1	~87.4	~17.1	[33]
	EBV	~15.6	~125.0	~8.0	[34]
	HIV-1	~7.0	~100.0	~14.3	[35]

Figure E
"Summary table for the antiviral activity of the Major Compounds in this Herbal Mix"

4. Discussion

As is well known, each component of the mixture has its own anticancer and antimicrobial mechanisms. Refer to Figures A, D, and E for the comparative profile of individual herbs and compounds :

- **Curcumin** can induce apoptosis and inhibit metastasis by modulating NF- κ B and p53 pathways.
- **Gingerols** suppress proliferation and down regulate inflammatory mediators.
- **EGCG** in green tea inhibits tumor growth by blocking PI3K/AKT and MAPK pathways.
- **Artemisia herba-alba** promotes ROS generation and DNA fragmentation.
- **Thymoquinone**, the active constituent of *Nigella sativa*, modulates oxidative stress and apoptosis-related genes.

And with reference to this presented research, the polyherbal extract exhibited a dose-dependent cytotoxic effect on HepG2 liver cancer cells, with an IC₅₀ value of 54 μ g/mL {The IC₅₀ "half maximal inhibitory concentration" represents the concentration of the extract required to inhibit 50% of cell viability}. This indicates that the extract possesses **notable antiproliferative activity against the HepG2 hepatocellular carcinoma cell line.**

In contrast, when tested on normal mouse liver cells (used as a model for non-cancerous tissue), the extract demonstrated a significantly higher IC₅₀ value of 250 μ g/mL. This suggests that the normal cells were less sensitive to the extract's cytotoxic effects, highlighting a degree of safety toward healthy tissue. An SI value greater than 3 is generally considered to indicate selective cytotoxicity toward cancer cells, meaning the compound is more toxic to cancer cells than to normal cells. Therefore, an SI of 4.63 **reflects a promising degree of selectivity, suggesting that the polyherbal extract preferentially targets hepatocellular carcinoma cells over normal cells.**

These findings support the potential of the polyherbal formulation as a candidate for further development as a selective anticancer agent, **particularly for liver cancer.** Further in-depth studies including mechanistic evaluations, in vivo testing, and toxicity profiling are warranted to confirm its therapeutic potential and safety.

5. Conclusion

The polyherbal extract composed of *Curcuma longa*, *Zingiber officinale*, *Camellia sinensis*, *Artemisia herba-alba*, and *Nigella sativa* exhibited significant cytotoxic activity against HepG2 hepatocellular carcinoma cells, with an IC₅₀ value of 54 μ g/mL, while demonstrating considerably lower toxicity toward normal mouse liver cells (IC₅₀ = 250 μ g/mL) ; (Ref. Fig. C). The resulting selectivity index (SI) of 4.63 indicates a **preferential cytotoxic effect on cancer cells compared to normal cells.**

These results suggest that the extract possesses **promising selective anticancer potential**, supporting its further investigation as a natural therapeutic candidate for the treatment of liver cancer. Future studies should aim to elucidate the underlying mechanisms of action, validate efficacy in in vivo models, and assess the safety profile through comprehensive toxicological evaluations.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest. However, we must point out that this preliminary research on liver cancer is just the first step in the development of an effective drug. It will undergo legalization and relevant experiments before it can be completed and released.

Therefore, the researcher hopes that other scientific, academic, or research organizations will build on this research and bring it to fruition as an effective drug against liver cancer, for the benefit of humanity in the fight against this and other cancers.

References

1. Kunnumakkara AB et al. Curcumin inhibits proliferation, invasion, angiogenesis and metastasis of different cancers. *Cancer Lett.* 2008 ; 269 (2) : 199–225.
2. Zhang M et al. Selective cytotoxicity of curcumin on human cancer cell lines. *Anticancer Res.* 2009; 29 (10) :3795–3801.
3. Habib SH et al. Ginger extract inhibits proliferation and induces apoptosis in cancer cells. *Molecules.* 2008 ; 13 (10) : 2736–2746.
4. Shukla Y, Singh M. Cancer preventive properties of ginger. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2007 ; 45 (5) : 683–690.
5. Yang CS et al. Molecular targets of tea polyphenols. *Mol Nutr Food Res.* 2006 ; 50 (2) : 170–175.
6. Suganuma M et al. Green tea polyphenols as cancer preventive agents. *Cancer Lett.* 1999 ; 114 (1-2) : 79–84.
7. Bouchelaghem S et al. Cytotoxic and antioxidant activities of *Artemisia herba-alba*. *J Biol Res.* 2015 ; 88 : 40–45.
8. Kordali S et al. Inhibitory effects of *Artemisia* extracts on human cancer cells. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2009 ; 47 (2) : 339–344.
9. Gali-Muhtasib H et al. Thymoquinone from *Nigella sativa* induces apoptosis. *Int J Oncol.* 2004 ; 25 (4) : 857–866.
10. Badary OA et al. Thymoquinone suppresses oxidative stress in hepatocarcinogenesis. *Int J Cancer.* 2001 ; 93 (5) : 667–673.

11. Nabil M. Abdel-Hamida, Shima A. Abassa, Ahmed A. Mohamedb, Daniah Muneam Hamid. Herbal management of hepatocellular carcinoma through cutting the pathways of the common risk factors. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 2018 ; 107 : 1246–1258.
 12. Tandon et al., *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 2021 ; Vol.12.
 13. Chen et al., *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2010 ; Vol.53 Issue 15 & 20.
 14. Anggakusuma et al., *Hepatology*, 2014 ; Vol.59.
 15. Kutluay et al., *Virology Journal*, 2008 ; Vol.373, Issue 2 : 239-247.
 16. Ghosh et al., *Antiviral Research and Phytotherapy Research*. 2021 ; 35 : 2296–2316.
 17. Nogueira de Melo et al., *Phytotherapy Research*, 2014 ; 28: 1806–1815.
 18. Chang et al., *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 2013 ; Vol.145 Issue 1 & Vol. 148 , Issue 2.
 19. Saha et al., *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 2021 ; Vol.12.
 20. Jang et al., *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 2021 ; Vol.102 : 561-565.
 21. Calland et al., *Journal of MDPI*, 2012 ; 4 : 2197-2217.
 22. Song et al., *National Center for Biotechnology Information*, 2005 ; 68 (2) : 66-74.
 23. Isaacs et al., *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 2008 ; Vol.52, No. 3.
 24. Carneiro et al., *Journal of Elsevier, Virology* 2016 ; 496, : 215-218.
 25. Astani et al., *Phytotherapy Research*, 2010 ; 24: 673–679.
 26. Li et al., *Microbial Drug Resistance*, 2017; Vol.23, No. 2.
 27. Wu et al., *UBMB Life Research*, 2006 ; Vol. 58 , Issue 8 : 480 – 486.
 28. Astani et al., *Evidence-Based Complementary & Alternative Medicine*, 2011.
 29. Melo et al., *Mem Inst Oswaldo Cruz, Rio de Janeiro*, 2017 ; Vol.112 (6): 458-468.
 30. Silva et al., *Journal of MDPI*, 2018 ; 10 (5) : 255-256.
 31. Ahmad et al., *Food Science and Nutrition* , 2021 ; Vol.9 , Issue 3 : 1257-1830.
 32. Raghunandhakumar et al., *Journal of Elsevier, Toxicology* , 2013 ; Vol.223, Issue 1 : 60-72.
 33. Salem & Hossain, *Journal of Elsevier, Immunopharmacology*, 2000 ; Vol.22, Issue 9 : 729-740.
 34. Malek A. Zihlif et al, *Sage Journals, Integrative Cancer Therapies*, 2013 ; Vol.12, Issue 3: 257-263
 35. Surabhi Chandra et al, *Sage Journals, Experimental Biology and Medicine* 2009 ; Vol.234 Issue 4.
-